

Pragmatic Presupposition of Newspaper Headlines on Children's Involvement in Terrorism in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Terrorism discourse in Nigeria, with its different manifestations, nomenclatures, and dynamics, has continued to attract investigations, particularly on how to curb the act, but the involvement of Nigerian children as child soldiers in the phenomenon, which could unveil how and to what extent they are available to be engaged by terrorist groups, has hitherto received less scholarly attention. This paper addresses this gap by examining the pragmatics of media portrayals of child soldiers in terrorism in Nigeria. The data, consisting of 105 headlines from five Nigerian newspapers between 2014 and 2021, was analysed using the pragmatic presuppositions and pragmatic act theory. Findings reveal predominantly three presupposition triggers, namely recruitment, usability, and donation as signposts to child soldiers in Nigeria, manifesting existential and lexical presuppositions. The triggers index context of terror with the ostensible use of words characterising activities such as bombing, killing, and attacking innocent Nigerians, and inferencing how children are deployed by different terrorist groups in the country. With the presupposed component of intentionality, the headlines not only inform, alert, indict, and urge, but also assert the indisputable involvement of children in terrorist acts. From the findings, it can be inferred as a pragmatic orientation that media reportage presupposes the vulnerability of Nigerian children in the hands of terrorists.

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Introduction

In contemporary times, terrorism has remained one of the most pressing security challenges confronting many nations across the world. In Nigeria, the phenomenon has manifested in different forms, ranging from insurgency and violent extremism to coordinated attacks on civilians and state institutions. Much of the existing studies have focused on operational means of terrorist groups, recruitment patterns, ideological motivations, and military responses (Onuoha, 2014; Comolli, 2015; Human Right Watch, 2016; Onuoha et al., 2024), relatively little attention has been paid to the involvement of children in terrorist activities. The recruitment and deployment of children as combatants, informants, and suicide bombers has long been recognised as a violation of international humanitarian and human rights norms (United Nations, 1989; UNICEF, 2018), but the linguistic and media-oriented perspective of how children's

involvement in terrorism is constructed and communicated in public discourse has not been sufficiently systematically investigated (Olajimbiti, 2025).

The media play a crucial role in shaping public understanding of terrorism and its associated actors. Crime news, involving children, usually provides the ground for influencing the public stance, mirrored in the news, which influences the authors' decisions (Tabbert, 2015: 3). Newspaper headlines in particular function as discourse tools that summarise events, frame narratives, and influence readers' interpretations of complex social issues, including the involvement of children in terrorism. Through linguistic choices, presuppositions, and other pragmatic cues, headlines, in most cases, subtly encode assumptions about responsibility, agency, and victimhood. Therefore, the media's portrayal of children's involvement in terrorism may reveal underlying societal assumptions about vulnerability, coercion, and culpability. In the context of Nigeria's insurgency, it is significant to examine assumptions on children's involvement in order to unpack how narratives about child soldiers are constructed by the media.

From a linguistic perspective, pragmatics provides useful insights to uncover implicit assumptions entrenched in discourse. Ake in this context is presupposition, a pragmatic concept which provides a framework to investigate how language users encode assumptions and intentions beyond the literal meaning of words. In media discourse, presuppositions often function as backgrounded information that readers are expected to accept as given, thereby shaping interpretations and framing realities. On this premise, this study examines presuppositions in newspaper headlines to identify how the involvement of children in terrorism is implicitly represented in the Nigerian media space. Very limited scholarly attention has been directed to this area of research, which has the potential to unpack the pragmatic construction of child soldier narratives in Nigerian media. The few existing studies tend to emphasise the operational tactics of insurgent groups (Comolli, 2015), the humanitarian consequences of child recruitment (UNICEF, 2017), leaving out the linguistic mechanisms through which these realities are reported. This gap is significant because media discourse not only reflects events but also participates in constructing social meanings, public attitudes, and policy conversations surrounding terrorism and child protection. With these in mind, this study examines the pragmatics of media portrayals of child soldiers in terrorism-related headlines in Nigeria, with the aim of identifying pragmatic features of presupposed information about children's involvement in terrorist activities and their implications. Ultimately, this study contributes to discussions on terrorism discourse, media framing, and child vulnerability in conflict settings within Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

The literature around child soldiers is centred on two perspectives: children as victims and as perpetrators. These perspectives indicate that children are implicated not only as collateral damage but as victims, and in most unsettling instances, as active perpetrators. This dual reality complicates terrorism efforts. The perspective of children as victims echoes the vulnerability of children to terrorist activities within three broad contexts. First, when families are shattered by terrorist attacks, children are rendered homeless and orphaned, thereby often stranded, tortured, and sometimes recruited as child participants in armed internal conflicts with terrorist groups. The second context shows how children are increasingly exploited and recruited by

terrorist and militant groups to become child soldiers or suicide bombers. During this process, terrorist groups adopt different strategies to groom and indoctrinate children easily because they are less likely to resist their ideology. The final context relates to how children become more vulnerable when government actions aimed at crushing militancy mistakenly touch innocent citizens, through which children are directly or indirectly affected. This perspective of victimhood is the dominant and widely researched (UNICEF, 2018; Drumbl, 2012), with a body of work spanning psychology, sociology, and medicine, that considers harm inflicted upon children in conflict zones.

From a psychological perspective, studies have focused on the consequences of trauma of exposure to violence, loss, and instability on a child's development. Hoven et al. (2003) and Brown and Goodman (2005) detail the high prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, depression, and other emotional disturbances among children affected by terrorism. These studies found that children suffer from the loss of loved ones, witness horrific acts, and live in a constant state of fear, leading to serious emotional trauma that can persist throughout their lives. The sociological perspective broadens this lens to examine the societal-level impacts. Denov and Shevell (2019) claim that terrorism displaces vast numbers of children, turning them into refugees or internally displaced persons. This displacement severs their connections to home, community, and education, robbing them of a stable environment essential for growth. The study observes that the breakdown of social structures and family units leaves children exceptionally vulnerable to exploitation and further harm. Furthermore, the medical perspective highlights the immediate physical dangers and long-term health crises. Berents (2020) and reports from organisations such as UNICEF (2020, 2025) document the direct casualties of attacks, as well as the indirect consequences such as malnutrition, disease, and lack of access to healthcare that plague children in conflict-ridden areas. In this context, children are passive recipients of violence, their innocence crushed by forces beyond their control.

On the other hand, the perspective of children as perpetrators presents a more complex reality. A significant body of literature investigates the phenomenon of children as active participants, collaborators, and perpetrators of terrorist acts. This vista complicates the simple victim/perpetrator binary by suggesting that children can be both at once. Bloom and Horgan (2019), who work on mechanisms of children recruitment, claim that children are drawn into terrorist organisations through various means, ranging from coercive abduction to seemingly voluntary enlistment, driven by a "culture of martyrdom", peer pressure, or the promise of security and belonging. Terrorist groups exploit children's vulnerability to indoctrinate them and deploy them in various roles, such as spies, cooks and suicide bombers. This reality poses challenges from a legal perspective. As Novrita, Syauqullah, and Logahan (2019) and Squiers (2015) explore, the legal status of a child soldier is fraught with ambiguity. International law struggles to reconcile the child's status as a victim of illegal recruitment and a perpetrator of heinous crimes. This raises difficult questions about accountability, justice, and rehabilitation. Are these children criminals who should be prosecuted, or are they victims who require protection and support? The legal frameworks are often inadequate for addressing this complex duality. How all these are represented and

constructed by the media, particularly from a linguistic perspective in the Nigerian context, is the focus of the present study.

Of course, connecting these perspectives is the crucial role of media and language in representing and, ultimately, constructing the public's understanding of child soldiers. Comer et al. (2008) suggest that the node of linguistics and media studies offers a vital lens for unpacking how terrorism is portrayed. News headlines are potent in this regard as their framing guides readers' interpretation before the main article is read. News headlines summarise the main content in concise language, vividness, and attractiveness to entice readers and stimulate their enthusiasm for reading. Headlines typically employ syntactic compression, ellipsis, nominalisation, and a preference for short lexical items to convey maximum information within limited space (Dor, 2003). These linguistic choices allow headlines to provide concise summaries of news stories while maintaining readability and immediacy (Bell, 1991). This condensed form of language functions not only as a summary of the news story but also as a discursive tool that shapes readers' attitudes and expectations toward the content of the article (Hadidi, Taghiyev & Ahmadova, 2022; Basenko & Radchenko, 2020). Recent studies treat headlines as powerful discourse units that mediate meaning, ideology, and audience interpretation within the communicative practices of journalism (Dor, 2003; Osisanwo, 2024). In the context of the present study, pragmatic presupposition holds an important position in meeting the requirements of conciseness, vividness, and attractiveness of news headlines and how they can unpack background beliefs as part of common ground shared with the audience. On this note, the argument of the present study is further strengthened, given that extant studies on the presupposition of headlines covering children's issues, especially their involvement in and effects of terrorism on them, have been hardly touched in the Nigerian context.

Theoretical Orientation: Presupposition and Pragmatic Act Theory

Presupposition is described as an implicit assumption or background belief relating to an utterance whose truth is taken for granted in discourse. Communication normally takes place against a background of beliefs or assumptions which are shared by the speaker and their audience, and which are recognised by them to be so shared (Stalnaker, 1999). Pragmatic presupposition describes the implicit assumptions or background beliefs a speaker takes for granted as already known by the listeners or readers, essential for making meaning in any communicative exchange. It is similar to other technical terms in pragmatics, such as social appropriateness, mutual knowledge and common ground (Clark, 1996) between speaker and hearer while communicating. The linguistic expressions that imply or alert readers or listeners of certain presuppositions in communicative exchanges are called presupposition triggers (Valeika and Verikaite, 2010). Common presupposition triggers include: definite description, factual verbs (regret), change-of-state verbs (stop), iteratives (another time, again), comparatives, and cleft sentences. For instance, in "It is surprising that Bolu has stopped smoking," the assumption is that Bolu used to smoke, which is made known by the change-of-state verb "stopped". Furthermore, Yule (1996) identified six presupposition types: existential, factive, non-factive, lexical, structural, and counterfactual. The presupposition types relevant to the present study include lexical presupposition, which has to do with using one word to imply that another meaning

will be understood. Existential presupposition assumes the existence of entities named (NPs) and structural presupposition, which captures the assumption associated with the use of certain structures (when, where, before, etc.).

In order to properly capture the presupposed intentions (Ippolito, 2003), an aspect of Mey's (2001) pragmatic act theory is adopted on a complementary note. Pragmatic act theory provides a framework to analyse what people actually do with language in context, rather than what utterances mean in isolation. The theory has two parts: activity and textual, but only the textual part is employed in this study to analyse implicit intentions in the linguistic choices of the sampled news headlines. The textual part, which involves linguistic forms and structures used to perform practices, is instrumental to how communicative intentions are tracked. In this case, the agential actors and their roles in the news headlines and assumed shared situational knowledge constitute contextual cues to interpret certain intentions projected in news headlines on child soldiers in Nigeria.

Research Methods

The dataset comprises 105 newspaper headlines purposively selected from five major Nigerian newspapers: The Punch, The Nation, The Guardian, The Tribune, and Premium Times. These newspapers were chosen due to their national circulation, editorial influence, and ideological diversity within Nigeria's media landscape. A stratified sampling technique was employed to ensure temporal and institutional representation. Three headlines were selected from each newspaper per year, as the data span seven years (2014-2021). This period was selected because it captures heightened reportage on terrorism and insurgency in Nigeria, particularly involving children. Only headlines that explicitly or implicitly referenced children's involvement in terrorism were included. Headlines were sourced from the online archives of the selected newspapers to ensure authenticity and accessibility. The study adopts a qualitative approach. The approach is anchored in presupposition theory and aspects of pragmatic act theory. This combination enables the study to account for both implicit assumptions and contextualised meanings in the sampled headlines. Each headline was considered in the coding process as a site of interaction between explicit information and implicit presupposition. Attention was given to the dual-voice structure inherent in news headlines: editorial voice and source voice, in order to account for how intentions are layered, mediated, and recontextualised. Data were analysed qualitatively using a discourse interpretive technique. Patterns of presupposition and intentions were identified across the dataset and grouped into recurring pragmatic categories. On ethical considerations, the study relies on publicly available newspaper data and does not involve human subjects. Also, given the sensitivity of terrorism and children's vulnerability, the analysis was conducted with scholarly objectivity and ethical sensitivity.

Results and Discussion

The analysis is structured into two sections in line with the objectives of the study. The sections are 4.1. which presents presuppositions indicating children's involvement in terrorism, and 4.2. which reflects pragmatic functions of the presupposed information. These are analysed in turn.

Presuppositions Indicating Children’s Involvement in Terrorism

Presuppositions identified in the dataset involve around three discourse issues about child soldiers’ activities, which are donation, recruitment and usability. The sampled headlines pragmatically convey these activities as assumptions which are unveiled through presupposition triggers.

i. Presuppositions involving the donation of children

In this category, the presupposed information relates to how the newspaper editors assume that readers of headlines already know that children are being donated to terrorist groups. Three presupposition triggers mostly deployed in this context are the change of state verb, “stop”, the contextual use of “donate”, and nominal entities. These are exemplified by the following texts.

Texts

1. Army: **Stop** Donating Children to Suicide Bombers (The Nation, Aug 6, 2017)
2. **Stop** Donating Your Children as Suicide Bombers- NCWS Urges Parents (The Nation, Aug 8, 2017)
3. Boko Haram Attacks: Parents **Donating** their Girls for Suicide Bombing – Army (The Punch, August 6, 2017)
4. Kano Suicide Bomber Says Father **Donated** Her to Boko Haram (Premium Times, December 25, 2014)

What triggers the presupposition in Texts 1 and 2 above is the lexical word “stop”, which presupposes that some people are engaged in the activity of donating children to suicide bombers. Also, “donating children” assumes the existence of a practice where children are handed over for the purpose of bombing. The use of “army” and “NCWS” presupposes the existence of the institutions in the Nigerian context and signals a background assumption that readers know the source of the information. In this communicative context, the shared knowledge of the army and the North-Central Women Society constitutes part of the given information as institutions felicitous enough to make such claims and known involvement of people supplying children for attacks. Therefore, the change of state verb, “stop”, introduces a demand that the practice should cease, thereby framing it as a moral imperative. Therefore, the directive illocutionary force projected by “stop” reinforces a command and urgent appeal to the culprits to end the act.

Texts 3 and 4 present an example of lexical presupposition, triggered by “donating” and “donated”. In this context, the verb “donate” presupposes a voluntary giver and an intentional act of transfer of a valuable entity. Text 3 particularly presupposes that parents, who are framed as actors willingly transferring their daughters to the receiving institution, Boko Haram, for the act of suicide bombing. The headline assumes background coercion, fear and threat, and foreground parental culpability. The assumption here is that parents have the capacity to donate, whether denied or not. This is corroborated by the contents of Text 4, where a father is constructed as the sole decision-maker, reflecting familiar betrayal because he is supposed to protect the girl child he donated to Boko Haram. In this sense, the verb “donated” indicates the voluntariness of the act. Therefore, these headlines do not argue that parents donated

their children for suicide bombing but presuppose it. Readers are guided away from questioning whether the donation of children for the act of terrorism occurred, to why parents would do such a thing. Through the lexical presupposition, triggered by “stop” and “donate”, newspaper headlines background coercion and foreground parental agency, thereby constructing parents as complicit actors and children as transferable resources within the context of insurgency in Nigeria.

ii. Presuppositions involving recruitment of children

Recruitment of children for the act of terrorism is defined as “compulsory, forced and voluntary conscription or enlistment of children into any kind of armed force, armed group or terrorist or violent extremist group” (United Nations, 2017, p.5). Headlines in this category presuppose that children are being recruited for this purpose. This taken-for-granted assumption manifests lexical, existential, and structural presupposition types as triggered by certain noun phrases, wh-elements, and change-of-state verbs.

Texts

5. UN **Removes** Civilian JTF in Borno from Child Recruiter List (The Nigerian Tribune, Oct 19, 2021)
6. Boko Haram, ISWAP Recruiting **Child Soldiers**- Army (The Punch, Jan. 23, 2021)
7. **How** Boko Haram Recruits Children in Northern Nigeria (The Punch, 2019)
8. Boko Haram Recruiting Child Soldiers, Military **Alert** Parents (The Guardian, Aug. 15, 2020)

In Texts 5 and 6, children’s recruitment is backgrounded as an accepted reality and naturalises this interpretation in the events of insurgency. Text 5 provides an example of existential and factive presuppositions as triggered by the verb “remove” and the noun phrase “child recruiter list”. The existence of a child recruiter list wherein Civilian JTF was included, particularly by the UN, enhances the validity of the assumption. The legitimacy of the UN to classify the Civilian JTF as a child recruiter validates the historical fact of the recruitment of children for terrorism. Therefore, the verb “remove” presupposes and connotes institutional rehabilitation and legitimacy restoration of the Civilian JTF. Meanwhile, the progressive form of recruitment and the noun phrase (NP) “child soldiers” in Text 6 trigger the presupposition that recruitment is currently happening and the existential fact that children are already functioning as combatants. The NP “child soldiers” presupposes that such a phenomenon is a meaningful category in this conflict.

In Texts 7 and 8, triggers such as “how” (wh-interrogative), “recruit” and “children” presuppose the existence of child recruitment as a systematic practice tied to Northern Nigeria. These triggers assume current, active recruitment of children and the verb “alert” assumes that parents are positioned as potential gatekeepers to prevent the act. The presupposition triggers also background the contestability of child recruitment and foreground the existence of children’s militarisation.

iii. Presuppositions involving usability

The background assumption that readers are already aware that children are being used for terrorist activities is implicitly highlighted by editors in the construction of the Newspaper headlines. The dataset shows how children are presupposed as usable

instruments within suicide bombing discourse in Nigeria. This assumption is triggered by the use of change of state verbs, nominal entities (NPs) and *wh*-elements. These characterise only lexical and existential presupposition types as they project children as deployable instruments in the hands of terrorist groups in Nigeria.

Texts

9. **Why** Boko Haram Uses Women, Children as Suicide Bombing- Study (The Nigerian Tribune, Aug 13, 2017)
10. **Stop** Using Children as Suicide Bombers, UNICEF Tells Boko Haram (The Punch, Sept. 16, 2017)
11. U.S. **Indicts** Borno Govt. over Use of Child Soldiers (The Premium Times, July 29, 2015)
12. UNICEF **Urges** Boko Haram to **Stop** Using Children as Suicide Bombers (The Premium Times, Sept 16, 2017)

Through triggers such as “*wh*-element (*why*)”, “*uses*” and “*children*”, Text 9 presents an assumption that Boko Haram uses women and children as suicide bombers as an existential presupposition. In this case, women and children are framed as usable means, and the terrorist group has reasons for using them. The headline neutralises the instrumentality of children by shifting attention from the immorality of using children to the rationale behind their use in the ongoing insurgency in Nigeria. This way, children are discursively positioned as strategically useful assets in the hands of the group. Text 10 shows how triggers such as “*stop*” and “*using*” are used to indicate a factive presupposition that children are currently being used as suicide bombers. The progressive implication suggests repeated practice, which the verb “*stop*” foregrounds. This verb presupposes that the practice is established. These background assumptions in both examples foreground the moral illegitimacy of child exploitation and foreground children’s usability as a strategic resource in the hands of the terrorist group in the country.

Similarly, Texts 11 and 12 show presupposition of usability, which captures the implicit construction of children’s objects of strategic deployment as already-established reality. In Text 11, the key presupposition triggers are “*indicts*”, “*use*” and “*child soldier*”. This project factually presupposes that child soldiers have been used, for which the Borno State government has been implicated as an agent in the use. In this case, the verb “*indicts*” presupposes a recognizable practice subject to legal evaluation. This institutional culpability marks usability as a prosecutable act to assume the fact and existence of the act. The change of state verb “*stop*” in Text 12 presupposes an established pattern of how children are linguistically encoded as means in the terrorism act. The external moral authority that UNICEF represents further validates the presupposition of using children as military assets by a moral group.

Pragmatic functions of the presupposed information

The presupposition as a pragmatic phenomenon is capable of veiling the speaker’s communicative intentions in any discourse. In this context, apart from the strategic construction of headlines to draw attention to the presupposed information, the editors, through their choice of words, articulate sense and certain communicative intentions about the subject matter. These are unearthed through pragmeme, which refers to a

situated speech act, capturing socially and contextually entrenched communicative actions. In the selected headlines for this study, certain presuppositions indicate the following dominant communicative functions: informing, alerting, indicating, and urging. These are analysed in turn.

Informing Act

The informing act is primarily concerned with knowledge transmission by presenting new information or reporting a claim to the public without commanding or condemning it. In the context of this study, this communicative act manifests in presupposition categories oriented to donation and recruitment as illustrated in Texts 4, 5, and 7. As is typical of an informing act, which is realised through declarative structures and reporting verbs, the reporting verb, “says” in Text 4, signals reported speech. Here, the dominant force of the headline is to inform readers of a claim made by a social actor (an innocent girl) described as a suicide bomber. Although the headline indicts the father and evokes sympathy, the primary pragmeme is informing. Similarly, the structure of Text 5 is purely declarative and reportorial, which is typical of a newspaper headline. The verb “removes” signals a completed institutional action of the subject “UN”, indicating an official decision or policy update on the involvement of groups in the recruitment of children for terrorism in Nigeria. Therefore, the dominant function of the headline is to announce a change in status in the child recruiter list.

Alerting Act

This act relates to drawing urgent public attention to a danger, threat, or ongoing social problem about donating, recruiting, and using children for terrorist attacks in Nigeria. The act overlaps with warning discourse and uses emotionally charged or security-related vocabulary with the intention to draw vigilance and prompt precautionary behaviour. This act is dominantly deployed in presuppositions relating to the recruitment of children, as seen in Text 8. The headline explicitly contains the performative verb “alert”, which directly encodes warning and vigilance: “Military alerts parents”. The verb is used in a deliberate manner to shift the attention from neutral reporting to preventive communication. In this context, “military”, which represents institutional voice, increases the illocutionary force of the alert for preventive social function and provokes awareness, vigilance, and immediate parental attention. The mention of military invokes institutional authority and national security in alerting the public that such acts are occurring.

Indicting Act

The indicting act describes the situation of assigning blame, accusing, or morally condemning a person or group for wrongdoing. It is usually realised through declarative constructions that portray the accused as responsible agents. The act predominantly occurs in the headlines relating to presuppositions around donation and the usability of children for terrorist acts, as evident in Texts 3 and 11. In Text 3, the declarative structure, “parents donating their girls for suicide bombing”, presents the accusation as factual rather than speculative. In this case, parents are not only attributed the responsibility but also indicted for donating their children for suicide bombing. The accusatory force is further intensified by mentioning “Army”, which signals institutional legitimacy to issue such public blame and moral condemnation. Similarly, Text 8 serves

as a declaration of the US government's disapproval of the involvement of the Borno government in the use of child soldiers. This moral stance against the practice imposes guilt, condemnation, and criticism on the Borno government's action as unacceptable and a violation of human rights.

Urging Act

This describes the act of persuading or directing an audience to change behaviour or take preventive actions against child soldiers in Nigeria. The act is commonly marked by imperative verbs (stop) and explicit performative verbs (urge). Unlike pure warning, urging carries a behaviour-modifying intention by attempting to seek compliance or reform rather than mere awareness. This act is prominently used in headlines projecting presuppositions relating to the donation and usability of children for terrorism, as evident in Texts 12, 1, and 2.

Text 12 explicitly captures the performative verb, "urges", which encodes the pragmatic act of appeal to Boko Haram, not the general public, to "stop using children". The intention of the urging act in the headline is the behavioural discontinuation of child involvement in suicide bombing. Texts 1 and 2 present a similar pattern in the use of the imperative verb "stop" in the urging act. The structure of both headlines presupposes that the act is occurring and therefore requires immediate behavioural cessation. In Text 2, particularly, the speaker, NCWS (National Council of Women Society), represents a moral and advocacy body that strengthens persuasive rather than coercive authority in the discontinuation of this harmful practice.

Conclusion

The study, from a linguistic perspective, demonstrates assumptions of the existence of child soldiers and their engagement in terrorism in the Nigerian context. Through pragmatic presupposition triggers, three discourse issues were identified in the dataset: donation, recruitment, and usability of children. The dataset portrays Nigerian children as victims of terrorism because they are being coercively recruited and used by terrorist groups. Using children for terror attacks, suicide bombing, and killing portrays them as (forced) perpetrators. In this case, the assumed knowledge the newspaper editors shared with the readers constitutes the given information, while the new information relates to the incremental knowledge and communicative intentions of the speakers echoed in the headlines. Prominent communicative functions contextually projected in these headlines include informing, alerting, indicating, and urging.

Therefore, the headlines pragmatically suggest how readers accommodate the new information by fitting it into the background knowledge they presumably share with the speaker. Theoretically, the study submits that common ground, together with the role of lexical items, helps to formulate the pragmatic content of presuppositions in headlines. From the findings, it can be inferred, as a pragmatic orientation, that media reportage presupposes the vulnerability of Nigerian children in the hands of terrorists and assumes that they should be denied access to them. The study demonstrates that headlines function as strategic, context-driven communicative acts that shape public understanding through implicit meaning. It complements research on children and terrorism from a linguistics perspective.

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